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MASTER THESIS

**Between Algorithms and Autonomy: A Sociological Comparison of the
Experience of Freelancers from Ghana and South Africa on the Upwork
Platform**

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Abstract

Platform work is an increasingly important livelihood across Africa. Platforms like Upwork offer the possibility of working when, where, and how workers choose, but this promise of autonomy is complicated by opaque scoring systems, client reviews, and platform visibility. Drawing on semi-structured interviews with eighteen Ghanaian and South African knowledge workers, it analysed how freelancers on Upwork understand and make sense of the apparent trade-off between worker autonomy and control. Participants' narratives were taken as interpretations of experience rather than factual reports of events. Findings demonstrated that the promised freedom of platforms is often constrained by opaque scoring mechanisms, client control, unpaid visibility labour, and economic dependence on the platform. Ghanaian respondents often described Upwork as a response to economic pressure and weak institutional protection; South Africans more often framed it in terms of career opportunities and regulatory mismatch. Stress around the Job Success Score and fear of negative reviews were central issues in both national contexts. The workers described here do not passively try to overthrow algorithmic management; rather, they adapt their work practices in response to platform logic to maintain earnings and visibility. Using labour control theory, the paper demonstrated that control on Upwork relies less on supervision and more on platform rules, client demands and freelancers' self-adjustment.

Keywords: platform work, algorithmic control, autonomy, Upwork, Ghana, South Africa, labour control theory, Global South.

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Introduction

In recent decades, the nature of work has been radically changed due to the rapid spread of digital technologies (Acs et al., 2021). In the emerging platform economy, work is organised, not by fixed work locations or by long-term employer-employee relations, but through digital systems that coordinate clients and workers by bringing them together for separate tasks, done remotely and in-person (Alacovska et al., 2022). In this structure, a multitude of tasks are coordinated by the digital platform through automated processes regarding assignment of tasks, payments, and evaluation, many of which had been formerly handled by human managers or hierarchies (Vallas & Schor, 2020). The work has been dissociated from the office space, becoming accessible through a digital platform from anywhere, as long as there is access to the internet, which contradicts the stable, long-term work and predicted income, the social contract of work in the twentieth century. For some workers, platform work replaced the self-employment and informal contracting arrangements that had long existed outside standard employment. For others, it represented an entirely new route into income-generating work that was not available before digital platforms created globally accessible labour markets (Kalleberg & Vallas, 2018; Standing, 2010).

This new scale of the model is the entire world, and has started to remodel labour markets of both high- and low- income countries. Within the Global North, platform work is now a substantial part of the labour market. In 2024, approximately 38 per cent of US workers (about 64 million Americans) were gig workers or freelancers; an increase from years earlier due to a mature platform economy (Gig Economy Data Hub, 2025; MBO, 2025). In 2021, an estimate of 16 per cent of the US adults earned money on an online gig platform (Ravenelle, 2019). Also, the freelance platform market in the UK alone earned revenue over 412 million US dollars and about 1 out of 7 working-age people were engaged with platform work on weekly basis (Jones, 2021; Grand View Research, 2025). In the Global South, platform economy growth rates are even higher where the development is intertwined with different labour markets developed historically. Unlike many Western economies, where platform work has emerged amid deindustrialisation and the decline of stable manufacturing jobs, much of the Global South has never experienced large-scale industrial employment to begin with. Instead, these economies have long been characterised by widespread informal work, underemployment, and limited formal work creation (Chen, 2012; Meagher, 2016). These factors are instrumental in why countries like India and the Philippines have become the dominant providers of online labour. For example, the platform economy

workforce is estimated to increase from 7.7 million (in India) in 2020-21 to 23.5 million by 2030 (NITI Aayog, 2022), while the Philippines has over 1.5 million online freelancers, one of the largest sources of remote work platforms (ILO, 2021). Workers in these countries are supplying a significant part of global online work, contending for tasks posted mostly by North American and European clients. Such integration makes new earnings available to regions with lack of formal jobs, at the same time submitting workers to strong international competition and uncertain earnings (Graham et al., 2017).

Platform work in the African continent operates in a labour market that has been moulded by colonial past, structural adjustment and a limited degree of industrialisation. The change to platform work in Africa, as in various other countries in the Global North, does not represent a break with or a movement from a broad system of precarious, formal employment but rather adds to economies already dominated by high levels of informality, where the bulk of the labour force operates in self-employment, casual wage employment, and unregistered small-scale businesses (Oya, 2019). In Ghana, the informal economy makes up more than 80 per cent of total employment, and it is defined as work without contracts and with the absence of social protection, income and continuity (WIEGO, 2020). South Africa has a developed formal economy but also high structural unemployment and a massive informal economy. In these conditions, work provided via a platform, rather than representing a shift away from industrial age work and jobs, acts more like the extension of existing informality onto a digital platform. Between 38,000 and 258,000 Ghanaians work via a digital platform, compared with approximately 30,000 workers in South Africa (Fairwork, 2023). The key element is not so much informality, but the weak enforcement of labour rights and lack of resolution mechanisms; a worker in Ghana or South Africa with no recourse against unfair ratings or withholding of payments can more directly see the penalty associated with algorithmic sanctions. Whilst advanced economies are currently struggling to accommodate the implications of new work structures within their existing labour law systems, in many African countries, a nascent platform economy emerges in a context of weak, inconsistently applied labour standards, further enabling digital platforms to pursue business strategies that do not adhere to strong labour protections.

A comprehensive understanding of this shift demands an explicit definition of the processes that govern platform work. Unlike previous informal, dyadic work relationships where workers interacted directly with customers, platform work creates an algorithm that intervenes between the worker and the customer. Algorithms govern visibility, assign opportunities, determine ranking, and read clients' feedback as reputational signals on Upwork and other

platforms. By converting ratings into scores, automation also creates a novel type of surveillance-less through direct monitoring and more through an invisible control of the access to opportunity (Kalleberg & Vallas, 2018; Wood et al., 2019). Through algorithmic mediation, the work experience of the platform labour produces its central contradiction, giving up freedom to live in an experience of constant economic insecurity. Workers have nominal freedom as they are free to work when, where, and what they want to; however, their income is tied to client ratings, which algorithmically translate into reputation scores about which they know nothing and which determine the assurance of future work. Visibility will spike, then disappear; one disgruntled client could sink a worker's reputation and ranking, and workers globally will struggle for bids at decreasing price points. Income insecurity and unpredictable evaluation are not an individual's burden but an algorithmic, institutional reality.

These dynamics raise a scientific problem that existing research has not fully addressed: how do workers in specific national contexts interpret and navigate the tension between formal autonomy and algorithmic control on digital labour platforms? This is a particularly relevant question in the Global South, where the nature of institutions, reliance on income, and options to exit platform work diverge from those examined in the majority of research on platform labour. While much work already exists documenting how platforms constitute labour through algorithmic ratings, opaque rankings, and shifts in economic risk onto workers (Kalleberg & Vallas, 2018; Rosenblat & Stark, 2016). There is also evidence that workers react differently to platform labour conditions depending on their socio-cultural context. So, although in some countries the workers were compelled to utilise informal guidance, cooperation and teamwork to attract attention and bargaining with clients, in some others they tend to apply more individualised and competitive strategies on the grounds of specific labour norms (Jarrahi et al., 2020; Schor et al., 2020). These variations demonstrate that platform work does not operate globally in a uniform way; instead, it is shaped through workers' identities, their economic options, and their institutional settings. Far less is known about what happens in the Global South.

This paper answers this question by looking at freelancing in two African countries with different institutional arrangements: Ghana and South Africa. These are two digitally connected, sub-Saharan African countries with significant Upwork communities but significant differences in the structure of their labour markets, institutional capacity and degree of institutional protections, that they are good sites for testing how national context influences platform control experience. The choice of Ghana and South Africa makes it possible to test how platform-mediated labour is formed by disparate

institutional and legal histories. Despite being a foreign platform, primarily unregulated by national labour laws, workers do not enter the online market with no preconceptions. They enter with existing expectations, vulnerabilities and risk strategies informed by their understanding of national labour systems. Ghana has had 20 years of failed regulation and enforcement thus, even though the 2003 Labour Act exists, the majority of workers at the informal and basic level are unfamiliar with it and are used to self-propulsion and negotiation (Aryeetey & Baah-Boateng, 2015; Tsikata & Akua-Anyidoho, 2021). Unlike most countries, South Africa seems to have one of the most advanced and strong labour law systems in the world, with post-apartheid labour legislation as reflected in the Labour Relations Act and the Basic Conditions of Employment Act (Webster, 2020; Webster et al., 2017). Even so, and despite this protective history, high structural unemployment forces most South Africans to be in the informal segment and thus excluded from formal coverage. These contrasting histories are what inform the way a worker in Accra versus Johannesburg understands a rating or how they might choose to compete for a global work.

The literature commonly sees technology as the only important factor; however, this study does not do that. It does not just focus on technology but the practice of the workers working in the platform economy to illustrate the social consequences of the platform economy. The paper studies gig workers in two countries in order to look into how people negotiate the tension of “freedom” as self-employed and “control” by invisible algorithms through examining the reviews of clients on their jobs. The article views the workers as agents who construct and interpret, bargain and conform to the rule of global marketplace instead of being subject that are dominated by the software (Anwar & Graham, 2020). Together, these cases show the ways that global platforms interface with local labour market realities to shape differing experiences of insecurity and opportunity. The paper will offer an overview of this interaction, presenting different perspectives across different sections. I started by summarizing existing literature related to the platform economy, with special reference to the way in which digital work facilitates and constrains workers. I focused particularly on Upwork as a site of professional knowledge work. I then presented the comparative framework applied in the research and the model employed to analyse the experiences of workers in Ghana and South Africa. The following sections contain the evidence that describes the actual strategies workers employ to manage visibility and reputation. I concluded by discussing what these findings reveal about the specific challenges of platform work in developing economies and how they can add to sociological conversations on labour and algorithmic management in the Global South.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Platform Work in the Global Economy

Around the world, new ways of earning a living have become part of everyday life. The manner in which work access has changed recently, and work assessment procedures used in relation to earnings have changed immensely (Kelliher & Richardson, 2012; Monks, 2023). The latter half of the twentieth century was primarily comprised of steady jobs; there are a multitude of reasons why app-based working has grown so quickly in recent times (ILO, 2021). This was, however, not an entirely new trend. It was the result of a historical process that dates back to the 1980s. Neoliberal economic restructuring, which intensified during the 1980s, modified the structure of capital-labour relations. At the same time as establishing the conditions for business to systematically dismantle the working class by privatising and deregulating, the decade opened up space for flexible and offshore labour to expand (Harvey, 2005; Okafor, 2010). And so, when digital technology entered the scene at the beginning of the 2000s, the necessary framework was already in place to allow for the division of this labour. Indeed, it seems to have been taking shape since the early 2000s, as major companies gradually withdrew from the direct management of employees. Weil (2014) points out that a separation occurred between ownership and work, as companies increasingly resorted to contractors, vendors, and autonomous units under brand names rather than hiring directly on their payroll, thereby centralising decision making while outsourcing workers' wages, health and safety and other employment regulations. Therefore, platform work itself may also be viewed as a new reorganisation of work as the old employment relations dissolved. As with past instances of labour reorganisation (mechanisation to factory work, factory work to decentralisation, etc.). This represents a qualitative difference, despite the connections between platform work and the prior neoliberal development processes (Joyce & Stuart, 2021).

The essential distinguishing feature of platform work is not the provision of labour insecurity, but that it is through algorithms that work is organised and managed, transnationally and digitally. The work-related formalisation has guided the previous cycles of pushing risk towards the workers, due to which there has been a flexibilisation and informalisation. Under platform work, this has been augmented due to the implementation of systems of ratings, reputation profiles, and reviews, which bring into play constant online assessments (Wood et al., 2019). Moreover, the choice is determined through the underlying rules of the system, its design, and evaluation metrics, which questions the traditional modes of management and fairness in the labour market. Often overlooked is the important distinction

between location-based and fully online gig work. Tasks tied to a location, such as ride-hailing and food delivery, depend on a centralised system to steer and control action in physical space (Anwar & Graham, 2021). Fully online platform work, like programming, design, or writing, can be performed anywhere, and the labour draws across time zones. The oversight workers are subjected to also varies depending on the type of work performed. Those doing location-based work often have their movements tracked continuously through the use of apps and sensors; those working online have their work shaped more by volatile demand and the pressure to stay visible and responsive on digital networks (Wood et al., 2019).

The global expansion of digital platform work has created a transnational labour market where workers from very different economic backgrounds compete for the same tasks. Within this global market, it is important to distinguish between two types of platform work. Location-based platforms such as ride-hailing and food delivery coordinate physical labour in a specific geographic area. Fully online platforms such as Upwork, Fiverr, and Freelancer draw labour across time zones without geographic limits. This study is particularly concerned with fully online platform work, the online work completed by workers situated in lower-income countries. While many studies present the platforms as free, open, and egalitarian spaces of competition, research has also demonstrated that inequalities are reproduced in digital spaces. An example is that workers situated in lower-income countries are more likely to be disadvantaged by discriminatory hiring signals or to receive lower rates of pay than workers in higher-income countries performing similar kinds of labour (Van Slageren et al., 2022). This, among other things, can create a 'race to the bottom,' or, as stated, the creation of a large, global labour surplus that drives down wages and further disadvantages skilled freelancers in obtaining a steady income (Graham et al., 2017). Given that the work is largely performed remotely, from one country to another, it is very difficult for national labour laws to police it and therefore protect the workers, who can be vulnerable. The rise of the platforms can therefore be viewed as a consequence of a general shift of risk from employers to individuals, while "flexibility" serves to conceal precariousness: workers spend considerable time unpaid doing things like setting up profiles, bidding for tasks, or staying visible to platform algorithms (Schor et al., 2020). In this way, digital platforms scale and standardise the fragmented, outsourced workplace, turning it into a high-tech model of work organisation (Joyce & Stuart, 2021; Weil, 2014).

2.2 Online/knowledge Platforms

When the arrangement and administration of jobs are put into practice, working online differs from working in an established physical workplace. This enables people, along with clients, to collaborate from anywhere in the world instead of at a specific location through online tools like Upwork or Fiverr (Anwar & Graham, 2021; Graham et al., 2017). Most jobs conducted remotely are through online digital platforms. Here, tasks may be quick and small, or they may require high skill and big detail. They might be incorporated into the construction of software, offering consulting services, or generating original, creative materials. Nonetheless, the way people are hired on the web is not like in offices. It is dependent on scores kept by apps, creating a transactional labour market where workers compete under unequal conditions. These worldwide connections matter; they are not neutral. Through the mechanisms of payment, infrastructure, rights, and relative bargaining power, the assignment of who gets the rewards and who bears the risk in platform work (Graham et al., 2017), determines the shape that these institutions are going to take. Consequently, platform work becomes an essential focus for investigating how global inequalities are reproduced through digital technologies.

Client ratings, along with the track of data platforms, carry a lot of weight. Due to these forces, who shows up next on a platform is often determined by numbers hidden behind screens. Establishing a reputation online that fosters trust is vital for digital work opportunities. Reputational capital is the asset, often acquired through good feedback and good scores, which informs others that you can be trusted and that you do well (Gandini, 2016; Rahman, 2021). These things are not constant; they are ever-changing. All these factors can work to make a small mistake a major one if a comment goes wrong. What can be seen from this is a huge burden put on workers to curate their own image online. The unpaid effort invested by workers in identity work, where the task is to create an attractive individual profile and a collection of work samples, then manage interactions to ensure a favourable impression (Blyth et al., 2022), all while maintaining one's online reputation, is what differentiates online knowledge work from other forms of gig work.

Completion of the works is not enough to have visibility on these platforms. It is an ongoing conversation and establishing a rapport with credibility over time. Decision-making, drawing boundaries, and reacting to client suggestions must all provide evidence of abilities (Jarrahi et al., 2020). What is perhaps most important, though, is how beneath these aspects of ordinariness lies the everyday interaction; these are the silent threads from which to weave one's self-perceptions and resolve the tension between wanting to be one's own master and needing to be subordinate. Although they are legally

free agents, freedom is limited in terms of practical control by virtue of app design. Time trackers allow for automatic response in response to conflict, and skill raters manage productivity, thus transforming the desire for freedom into a concealed means of exercising real autonomy (Blyth et al., 2022).

2.3 Labour Control and Knowledge Work

Understanding how control functions on digital labour platforms requires more than describing what algorithms do. It needs a framework that explains what control is for, what forms it takes, and how it is experienced by workers across different locations. Labour control theory gives that framework. Control is inherent in the labour process itself, which is why it remains an important issue in labour studies. To understand why, it helps to start with a basic economic reality: when employers purchase labour, they buy only the potential to work, not actual output. Turning that potential into productive activity requires ongoing management and control. It is evident that workers and employers are structurally opposite: the latter aims to optimise production with minimal costs, while the former intends to safeguard their own life and time. The purpose of control is to mediate the conflict and secure its management to the employer's benefit. Braverman (1974) pointed to the separation of work design from work performance as key to the capitalist control of labour. The separation of design from the worker was that thought processes, planning and decision-making about how work should be carried out are removed from the worker, into management. The worker is left to execute tasks whose design and purpose they had no part in determining. This deskilling serves a control function: workers who cannot plan their own work become more dependent on those who do. Braverman argued that this separation from intellectual labour was a main part of the capitalist labour process. (Edwards, 1979) later pointed out that there are three forms of control over wage labour in the factory and the office: direct personal supervision; control built into technology and work processes; and control built into the organisation's formal rules. His analysis focused on the factory and office, but there is no reason his conclusions could not be applied to the platform economy with reasonable accuracy. This is not so much a matter of employer control through the managerial hierarchy as a characteristic of the labour process itself.

According to Standing (2010), the impact of control differs due to market position. Workers who are non-regular and casual in nature do not enjoy the rights and protections available in the ordinary labour market and, thus, have no choice but to deal with economic coercion so as to exercise control over their work and work conditions (De Stefano, 2016; Standing, 2010). In the digital labour platform context, formal sanctions, informal ratings, loss of visibility,

and job matching control workers. The platform does not only exercise control through formal rules and sanctions but also through worker dependence for income. The workers at the centre of this study are particularly important in this respect. Writers, designers, developers, and virtual assistants are skilled workers. They enter platform work in the hope of preserving a greater degree of professional autonomy. Knowledge work is positioned complexly in the world, according to Sewell (2005). Knowledge work is based on creativity and autonomy but is nonetheless subject to numerous restrictions. At times these are similar to the styles of control found in direct types of labour, but they can also be more subtle and, in line with Barker's (1993) notion of concertive control, can be less apparent.

For online platforms, control is exerted through the star ratings, responsiveness expectations, and visibility rankings. While the workers are not being directly ordered to do anything, these mechanisms strongly encourage certain behaviours to ensure they remain competitive. However, this control is not evenly distributed among all workers. A stronger formal job alternative might result in a different algorithm penalty for a programmer in South Africa than for a writer in Ghana who uses Upwork to make a more significant part of their livelihood. Thus, control is a relational phenomenon, the impact of which on workers varies with their labour market position, their level of dependence on the platform, and their exit options.

In addition to situating algorithmic management within existing scholarship on work and employment, this theoretical framework provides concepts to understand the labour process through which power, dependence and inequality are embedded in the management of algorithmically-mediated work. The labour control framework also allows us to ask who benefits from keeping the algorithm opaque, and how workers in different positions are affected by management through algorithms. In particular, the framework is very useful for analysing how individual freelancers in different situations, such as labour market position, income dependency, and availability of alternatives, would make sense of and react to the same platform rules.

2.4 Opportunities, Risks, and Contradictions in Platform Work

Platform work can be viewed very differently among different researchers and workers, but first, it is essential to acknowledge the opportunities digital labour platforms present for structural changes in the labour market. Above all, new platforms create new opportunities for formal employment for a large number of people. Particularly in countries with high rates of unemployment and a lack of fixed-term or permanent jobs, labour on digital platforms can be a chance for income, especially for the younger

generation (ILO, 2021). Moreover, workers with low income can also earn money on these platforms as long as they have access to the internet. Creative jobs and self-employment have already, for a long time, presented the possibility to reach global markets, as new digital platforms, such as online freelance or gig-work platforms, also for people from the Global South, present the opportunity to be included in the new digital economy at a point in time where formal industrial employment has never been widespread (Steedman et al., 2022; ILO, 2021). However, the rise of platform work also has structural consequences for labour, especially concerning organisation, evaluation and work experiences. While the platforms see themselves as neutral intermediaries who merely link workers with clients (Gillespie, 2010), the systems through which people work on these platforms change how people approach and perceive work, enabling new forms of monopoly, insecurity, and inequality. The digital labour market faces various problems because its platform governance structure mirrors the development of contemporary economic work systems worldwide (Kellogg et al., 2020). The economic risk transfer process between platforms and workers is a major concern. The platforms enable this practice through their contractor classification system, which protects companies from standard employment responsibilities, including minimum wage payment, benefit provision and job security (De Stefano, 2016). The classification system creates a labour process that forces workers to handle all the effects of changing market demand, their unpaid work searching for tasks, and the negative results of dealing with difficult clients. The second aspect, which Anwar & Graham (2021) identified as flexibility, coexisted with insecurity. Rather, they can only pick the time to log in, but they are not allowed to choose when they will be seen, selected, or paid. The platforms retain full authority to suspend user accounts, thereby preventing users from earning money and showing content without providing any explanation for their actions (Rosenblat & Stark, 2016).

Algorithmic management, on the other hand, complicates the calculation of these issues by embedding commands within the platforms' technological intermediaries. The workforce operates under automated systems that distribute work tasks and perform profile evaluations and performance assessments. The operation of these systems is with trimmed transparency. As a result, workers are left to deduce the rules that control them to their advantage. The entire process of worker client acquisition involves three stages, which include ID expansion, bidding strategy modification and communication method adjustment to handle algorithmic systems (Rahman, 2021). This "reactive" stance towards untraceable evaluation instruments creates a work environment characterised by obscurity, where workers have to keep adjusting to regulations they do not know. According to Eyert et al. (2022), the invisible

operations of algorithmic systems control what users see and determine which workers receive labour recognition while others remain invisible. Some studies highlight that algorithmic classification systems are the very means that introduce social hierarchies by favouring workers from specified geographic areas, ethnic or demographic groups, and thus affect workers' opportunities on the platforms (Muñoz et al., 2024). The three main ways biases appear in these systems are patterns in client preferences and platform design, and in the data used to train algorithmic models. These inequalities are further reinforced by global online labour markets, where workers from disadvantaged countries often compete in conditions where their labour is valued less because of wage competition and geographic bias, thereby reinforcing existing global economic inequalities (Graham & Anwar, 2019).

A reality that is becoming difficult to avoid is the extent to which platform work involves a considerable amount of unpaid labor. In order to gain clients and remain competitive, platform workers are forced to dedicate hours to unpaid tasks such as updating profiles, creating pitches, responding to clients, and managing their personal image online (Newlands, 2021). This “visibility work” is a necessary component for securing work, yet remains unpaid. Clients reap the rewards as workers engage in free labour that enhances the platform marketplace, while they themselves incur low costs. Conversely, an excessive number of work hours may yield low returns, draining the worker and pushing them toward financial despair (Schor et al., 2020). Platform work identity is also intensely demanded by the platform experience. While standard work offers roles and the social structures of the workplace in the construction of work identity and professionalism, app-based work challenges workers to craft work identity online through their profiles, where personal branding takes place, where certain skills are highlighted, certain strengths are emphasised, and interactions with each client are managed individually. They feel pressured to seem responsible, flexible and continuously “available,” altering their identities as necessary in response to platform signals and clients (Blyth et al., 2022). This process can be motivating for some, but for many, it adds another layer of mental and emotional strain.

More recent works no longer analyse platform work as necessarily good or bad, and point to the fact that different platform regimes lead to different outcomes—some platform work permits more meaningful independence, and some require high levels of unpaid labour, intense monitoring (Kalleberg & Vallas, 2018; Pulignano et al., 2023). As researchers called these differences ‘platform regimes’, or governance mechanisms, the workers are more or less truly independent. In the case of a digital platform, it is monitored by a single global governance entity, but researchers have shown that the experience of

governance does not feel uniform. Platform rules, rating systems, and algorithms that determine visibility are all the same worldwide, but the degree of autonomy that workers experience depends on what else is available in their local labour market, economic options, and regulatory environment. In labour markets with strong labour protections, workers may see platform rules as flexible. In markets with weak labour regulation and many alternatives, the same rules can feel rigid and risky. In this way, the effects of platform governance vary by country, resulting in differing levels of autonomy and insecurity. These differences in how workers interact within a single-platform regime are relevant to this research question, as they affect freelancers' perceptions of algorithms and their level of control.

However, workers do not solely surrender to algorithmic management. There is evidence that workers build strategies to adapt to, subvert and remould platform rules. Informal processes help workers develop an understanding of client behaviour, implicit platform logic, and efficient bidding strategies. The social counterforces to the technologies that exercise control occur when other workers accept, reject, create and hide information on their profiles and take the conversations off the platform in an attempt to renegotiate rules (Anwar & Graham, 2020). All of these are actions that demonstrate agency in the context of a system of control that does not necessarily provide broad latitude for its members. In addition to technology, social and economic contexts within which platform work takes place, as well as labour institutions, can shape platform work. Workers have more autonomy in areas in which labour regulation is strict and evenly applied. They might be able to return to traditional work or group together in collective action in an attempt to resist exploitation (Vallas & Schor, 2020; Wood et al., 2019). Platform workers are in stark contrast, where regulatory provisions are weak and implemented irregularly; varied and contradictory legislation facilitates minimal supervision of the platforms, which may lead to a situation where wages are deducted or unwritten and tacit rules to which workers still must conform (Heeks et al., 2021). These conditions set the boundaries within which workers operate and shape the strategies they adopt to survive on platforms.

Overall, platform work often balances between freedom and control. Although theoretically, workers are free to operate as they wish, their freedom in practice is delimited by the conditions dictated by algorithmic management, global competition, and continued reliance on unpaid labour (Blyth et al., 2022; Rahman, 2021). Consequently, it is not simply a case of technology influencing work practices and relationships; platform work is, above all, an issue of power, and is part of wider, ongoing transformations in labour. The research mentioned clearly names the primary drivers of platform work, but it doesn't tell us

precisely how they work as control. To go beyond description, it is necessary to use a theory that accounts for why control is practised, in what form, and why it affects workers in different positionalities differently. The next section, therefore, turns to labour control theory and its importance for knowledge work on digital platforms.

2.5 Platform Work in the Developing World

In developing countries, platform work is an extension of labour systems developed under a long history of unregulated employment, high unemployment and fragmented government control. In many African, Asian and Latin American countries, a large share of workers rely on informal work with irregular income and limited protection for more than half of the workforce (Chen, 2012; Meagher, 2016). In these situations, the introduction of digital platforms, rather than bringing about formal jobs, typically reinforces and expands informal ones. This is part of why platform work can grow quickly in the Global South, where formal work options are limited.

Developing economies also face persistent structural unemployment, rapid population growth and relatively narrow industrial sectors (Cook & Rani, 2023). For young digitally skilled workers, platforms can look like a practical route to income. According to ILO (2021), countries like India and the Philippines are increasingly emerging as important sources of online work, and this gives access to many workers to work remotely from their countries and take freelance jobs from overseas clients. The platforms can even allow workers to obtain income in foreign currency, which may be more reliable than employment opportunities in the local context (Anwar & Graham, 2021). Yet, international access increases the risk, opening opportunities for the global workforce. It is crucial to recognise the power imbalances at play and the unequal playing field. Workers from developing countries do not get the same opportunities as workers from developed countries when entering the international labour market, such as more reliable infrastructure and connectivity, and wider educational opportunities. It has been indicated that low pay is frequently attributed not to worker performance but to global inequality, and as competition intensifies, wage pressure can spread across sectors and push earnings down, and as competition increases, pressure on wages may migrate across industries, lowering earnings overall (Graham et al., 2017; Wood et al., 2019).

The outcome is also related to the institutional context. Compensation for wrong ratings and deactivations, or wage claims, is usually very limited. There is no or a narrow path in order to remedy the unjust rating and deactivation decisions and the non-payment of wages. Studies imply that weak

enforcement and fragmented regulation could give platforms and clients a large share of the power in relation to workers (Heeks et al., 2021; Rani & Furrer, 2021). Workers develop their own local communities and knowledge-sharing networks to deal with challenges. For example, many workers learn about platform norms and risk management through informal networks, which give them access to a support network and an ever-growing resource of useful tips on how to manage complex automated systems (Anwar & Graham, 2021). Platform work might also enhance or interplay with offline social hierarchies. For instance, the gender, race, and spatial divisions that are already evident in offline labour markets might get transposed and amplified (Hunt & Samman, 2020). In sub-Saharan Africa, functioning (as most contemporary digital platforms do) in the shadow of colonial legacies and structural adjustment programmes, along with a renewed informalisation of production, creates a specific landscape. In order to interpret the freelancers' experiences, understanding this context is essential.

2.6 Platform Work in Ghana and South Africa

History has a role in how people earn a living on platforms across Ghana and South Africa. What happened before still affects who does what today. In both Ghana and South Africa, the labour landscape was fundamentally altered by the wave of neoliberal reforms that swept through during the 1980s and 1990s. Under the guidance of global financial institutions, governments were subjected to structural adjustment policies that radically remade their economies (Konadu-Agyemang, 2000; Sebake, 2017). The state cut back on spending, sold off state-owned enterprises, and opened up markets to international competition. This led to a sharp fall in formal sector employment, a destruction of public sector jobs, and the creation of an informal and unstable sector where large numbers of workers would end up. The conditions created from this made platform work look more like business as usual rather than an innovation in precarious work (Heeks, 2021; Oya, 2019).

Systems developed over time regulate people's lives and livelihoods. In some cases, limited labour regulations are applied by the government of a country, while in other instances the policy is completely at odds with labour. The export-oriented sector is considered more beneficial than the labour in the latter case. Although there are laws on the books that may apply, the enforcement of those laws is often inconsistent and workers may wonder whom the laws protect. According to Graham & Anwar (2019 and ILO (2021), Upwork and other similar digital platforms do business across borders, often ignoring local labour legislation. Workers are deemed independent contractors and are denied employment benefits, while there is no clear way to demand

payment or remedy. In Ghana and South Africa, workers are typically classified as independent contractors. This classification excludes them from the ambit of existing laws such as Ghana's Labour Act 2003, creating significant legal loopholes (Fairwork , 2023; Mokofe, 2022). None of this happens in a vacuum. These years of inequality caused by globalization, alongside local factors like unreliable electricity and expensive internet, also contribute to this mix.

The history of Ghanaian labour goes back to colonial times, where British occupation aimed to foster the cultivation of cash crops and mining operations, which required an export-oriented labour force that was not strongly supported by labour unions or adequate protection mechanisms. After gaining independence in 1957 and the failed attempts by leaders like Kwame Nkrumah to industrialise, the country struggled to combat its debt and coup problems, leading to austerity in the 1980s. Wages and support systems offered by the state weakened, leaving people in search of individual opportunities and informal businesses (Aryeetey & Baah-Boateng, 2015). Currently, across Ghana, youth workers have a hand in shaping operations, especially in technology and services sectors. While the 2003 Labour Act claims to protect worker freedoms, it is inadequate when dealing with digital work and has not sufficiently provided a framework for support when an issue arises regarding unfair reviews or untimely payment for freelancers (Tsikata & Akua-Anyidoho, 2021). Workers cope, they learn new skills silently from networks of neighbours or on the Internet. But with generations of adaptation, it is easy to imagine that they shoulder a great burden, to work for world markets with little protection. Freelancers today find ways to push back as they deal with risks accumulated over the years, when nothing was managed properly (Anwar & Graham, 2021).

The story of labour in South Africa is linked with the history of apartheid, which, as a colonial and racial policy, institutionalised a divided economy. Whites occupied positions in modern industries, and black workers took jobs in poorly paid mines or as servants. Politics have changed since 1994: new legislation has been introduced (Labour Relations Act and Basic Conditions of Employment Act), and any disagreements have been resolved by different agencies, such as the Commission for Conciliation, Mediation and Arbitration, following Webster (2020). However, some decisions in the 90s, such as budget constraints, restricted progress, the labour market has remained divided, unemployment is still too high, and certain workers still see labour platforms as a pathway to finding employment, even if unstable (Bhorat et al., 2017). Some workers may look for help from the Commission for Conciliation, Mediation and Arbitration when there is conflict, but platforms and clients categorise workers in ways that prevent access to normal labour rights protections (Sibiya & du Toit, 2022). Roots tied to apartheid continues to influence workers who

are hired for positions, particularly when those positions are located overseas, as being Black already makes that a disadvantage (Fourie, 2018). Meanwhile, worker organisations in South Africa have had a long history of influencing how freelancers respond to push-back from platforms, and thus, this is reflected in online organising, solidarity networks and the emergence of a collective presence (Webster, 2020; Webster et al., 2017). The similarities and differences between the two cases demonstrates the extent to which history influences modern gig work: weak institutions encourage self-organization, which creates a level of security and vulnerability at the same time in Ghana, while more established worker rights help to frame responses in South Africa, while still resulting in insecurity in the platform context (Aryeetey & Baah-Boateng, 2015; Tsikata & Akua-Anyidoho, 2021; Webster, 2020).

This forms the core of a key institutional difference between the two countries. It is the configurations of labour regulation, the levels of enforcement and the rights that workers have in South Africa and Ghana. South Africa has a relatively stronger institutional configuration than Ghana, consisting of the Commission for Conciliation, Mediation and Arbitration (CCMA), labour laws, and a long history of struggle (Webster, 2020; Webster et al., 2017). Although these institutions offer little real protection to platform workers, they have relatively more opportunities for contestation with regard to unfair treatment and understanding what platforms set. In Ghana, with weak enforcement, limited protection for platform workers and labour markets historically characterised by informality, freelancers depend more on social networks, self-help and learning-by-doing to cope with the risks associated with platform work (Aryeetey & Baah-Boateng, 2015; Tsikata & Akua-Anyidoho, 2021). Thus, the national institutional context explains both the low reality of workers' protection in the two countries and workers' factual cooperation or resistance in platform work. Understanding these dynamics is essential for analysing how workers in contexts such as Ghana and South Africa interpret and navigate the tensions embedded in platform work.

2.7 Research Relevance and Justification

This study explored how the intersection of global platform governance and national labour histories creates an understanding of the experience of doing digital work. Existing global work has already shown that digital forms of labour management move the locus of power away from humans to machines (Vallas & Schor, 2020; Wood et al., 2019). The impact and operation of algorithmic frameworks have not been widely examined through the lens of the socio-economic context of the Global South. The literature has demonstrated that the concept of worker flexibility is actually accompanied by financial

precariousness and ubiquitous surveillance (Rahman, 2021). Ghana and South Africa were studied to understand how those pressures affect workers already functioning within the existing precarious labour frameworks, as opposed to just pointing out the existence of digital instability itself. The value of this research is to connect global patterns of work to local processes.

While the literature previously mentioned established how digital labour often reproduces past social inequalities by reconstituting them in new digital environments (Heeks et al., 2021). However, little is known about how African freelancers negotiate such environments, the role informal networks and temporary hacks play in allowing them to survive in anonymous markets (Anwar & Graham, 2021). Looking at Africa highlights how national history and structure can influence how work is carried out in the digital environment: in Ghana, for example, lack of state surveillance combined with decades of surviving with very few earnings is distinct from the existence of strict employment rules in South Africa, which aren't always accessible to those most in need (Aryeetey & Baah-Boateng, 2015; Webster, 2020). Because of these gaps, freelancers develop conceptions of freedom that are distinct, adapt their behaviour in reaction to threats, and act once these platforms exert more pressure. Despite the increased attention to digital labour, however, there are few qualitative comparative studies into how freelancers in African countries simultaneously use the same single platform (Webster & Masikane, 2023).

This gap is particularly relevant because research on a single country is not able to tell us what is produced by the architecture of the platform at the global level and what is being modified by the national conditions of institutionality. The analysis distinction requires a qualitative comparative research design in order to show them. Through a comparative investigation of Ghanaian and South African freelancers who operate on the same platform, it is possible to ascertain which elements of the experience on the platform are 'universally applicable' and which elements are 'nation-specific'. This will afford greater accuracy in knowing where the global platform governance meets with the national context of institutionality (Della Porta & Keating, 2008). An analysis of freelancers in Ghana and South Africa provides new insight into how the structures of global platforms, when mixed with national labor histories, create different experiences of autonomy and insecurity in African digital work. In this inquiry, the study will ask: How do Ghanaian and South African freelancers interpret and navigate the tension between autonomy and control on Upwork?

3. Data and Methods

This study is aimed at understanding how freelancers on the Upwork platform in Ghana and South Africa manage their autonomy at work and the extent to which they are controlled by the algorithm of the platform (Wood et al., 2019; Anwar & Graham, 2021). The selected countries for the study are Ghana and South Africa, as they are Global South countries with hugely different labour markets and institutional frameworks. Ghana's institutional framework is weak and self-employment has a long history there, while in South Africa, an official labour law framework exists but structural unemployment is high. This project aims to explore the meanings that freelancers in two countries make of platform work and how they navigate algorithmic control on Upwork. Building on insights gleaned from the literature, this study is based on the assumption that the experience of platform work will differ among workers in certain country contexts, without claiming total uniformity within countries. In my view, the country context, a worker's socioeconomic position, and labour market institutions will shape the control workers experience in platform work. In light of the varying labour market scenarios of Ghana and South Africa, the understanding of how the controlling algorithm of the platform works will vary in both countries; any comparative understanding further illuminates how the freelancers from the said countries navigate the platform. This chapter has given shades of the methodology used in the collection and analysis of data on the freelancers on the Upwork platform in Ghana and South Africa, while the upcoming chapter provides the findings of our study.

3.1 Research design and Upwork as Study Site

This paper explores the working conditions for online workers in one of the largest global online labour platforms, Upwork, where clients hire freelancers by posting jobs and freelancers submit proposals (bids) for the job. Upwork was chosen for three reasons. First, Upwork, a highly visible and one of the leading global online labour platforms, is particularly convenient for researchers to investigate the performance of platform-mediated freelancing (Green et al., 2018). Also, it hosts a wide range of knowledge-intensive and creative work, including writing, design, development, and virtual assistance, which are central to this study. Knowledge workers constitute one of the largest and fastest-growing segments on Upwork, with writing, design, development, and virtual assistance among the most frequently posted job categories on the platform. The focus on this group is further justified theoretically: knowledge work is typically characterised by high levels of professional autonomy, skill discretion, and self-direction (Sewell, 2005). This is a highly relevant group of workers, as they must live with formal autonomy and informal control through

algorithms, which is especially relevant in the African context. (Braesemann, 2022) reported that Upwork captured a considerable proportion of African online labour-platform web-traffic, and Fairwork (2023) estimated that a large number of South African and Ghanaian workers have now started generating income from these platforms. While platform-based freelancing can be conceived as work under flexibility and autonomy, workers on platforms like Upwork are still managed through remote control using ratings, platform rules and client feedback.

Figure 1. Online platform: sample Upwork Profile

The paper is concerned with knowledge workers on Upwork in Ghana and South Africa. Despite similarities, these two countries were selected for several complementary reasons. First, Ghana and South Africa are some of the most digitally connected and advanced economies within sub-Saharan Africa, with both high penetration of mobile broadband and advanced urban digital hubs (ITU, 2025; GSMA, 2025). Additionally, they show a considerable level of use of platforms such as Upwork with busy communities of freelancers in a

growing gig economy in the region (Fairwork, 2023). Besides those points, the institutions demonstrate substantial differences in the case contexts; a prime example of an institutional feature being labour market formalisation. The South African labour market is relatively formal with a relatively highly developed regulatory system, in contrast to the more informal labour market of Ghana (ILO, 2022). Such differences are also what make Ghana and South Africa appropriate as cases for a cross-national comparison within the established guidelines of cross-national case study design (Porta & Keating, 2008; Yin, 2003)

In order to investigate these processes of interpretation, I used a qualitative design. This approach specifically suited my research question because it gave a detailed examination of workers' own accounts of their experiences within the gig economy and an understanding of how they make sense of gig economy work rules and working conditions. Furthermore, qualitative inquiry gives the needed depth to understand how these freelancers relate their working conditions to their unique individual circumstances and their broader national labour market contexts (Creswell, 2014; Porta & Keating, 2008).

3.2 Data Collection Techniques

Data for this research were collected via a series of semi-structured interviews conducted remotely via online platforms such as WhatsApp and Google Meet. In each session, the workers were guided through the different dimensions of their experience of platform work by answering a series of questions, which they were then asked to illustrate and elaborate on. These allowed for an understanding of how workers describe and articulate their experiences of being managed by algorithms in the terms they choose.

The same interview protocol was used in both countries, but here it is used in a comparative perspective, examining how freelancers in the two contexts describe their experiences on the platform. The duration of interviews varied from 30 minutes to an hour and was arranged at the time preferred by the interviewee, at their convenience. All the interviews were tape-recorded with consent and were transcribed in full. The interview protocol was a backbone around which the interviews developed; it was designed to allow flexibility while seeking to establish the situated practice of freelancing on the platform. Information was sought about, for example, how freelancers decided to be active or inactive on the platform at different times, how they understood changes in their visibility on the platform, what they thought about the ratings given to their work, and how they managed the promise of autonomy implied by the fact that they worked on a platform, with the constraints introduced by

the algorithms that governed it. The work practices presented form the foundation of the situated accounts, to which section 3.5 is analysed thematically.

3.3 Sampling Method

To gather participants for this research, purposive sampling was used to select those who can give meaningful responses to the research question: How do freelancers in Ghana and South Africa interpret and navigate the tension between autonomy and control on Upwork? Given that it is required to assess their ranking algorithms, visibility scores, and client ratings, I had to recruit workers already using the platforms. Because it is one of the largest and oldest global job platforms, the Upwork workers only would serve better for between-country comparison. Purposive sampling is often used in qualitative research to find information-rich participants and has been used for studies of digital freelancing and platform work (Creswell, 2014; Huang et al., 2024; Nemkova et al., 2019). A small sample is appropriate here because qualitative case-based research sees depth and insight as more important than statistical representativeness (Small, 2009). The criteria for participants included (a) having and using an Upwork account, (b) completing at least three paid contracts, (c) working in Upwork categories termed knowledge-intensive, such as writing, graphic design, and virtual assistant roles, among others, and (d) living in Ghana or South Africa. The criteria ensured that they were familiar with the platform's algorithmic systems and can use this when recounting their experience. I used the same selection criteria in both countries to be able to compare freelancers from different socio-economic situations. Using social networking sites like Facebook groups, Telegram channels, or LinkedIn to recruit participants may limit your participants to those who are active users of the platform. Although it is a marginal limitation, this methodology did ensure that each participant was actively selling their labour to clients placing project ads. Further strategies may be needed to recruit freelancers who are less active. A final few participants were recruited using a second-wave snowball sampling approach, which I initiated when recruitment commenced falling off for this study. Snowball sampling requires contacting one connection from a social network link and identifying others who meet a certain criterion and may help with recruitment further. It relies on the willingness of participants; nonetheless, it is a well-used method for recruiting freelance digital workers who face a visibility problem (Biernacki & Waldorf, 1981)

According to **Table 2** (see Appendix A), all 18's pseudonyms, countries, cities, Upwork occupation categories and Job Success Scores at the time of the interview are shown in this table. The sample used for the research was the same

number of participants from Ghana and South Africa. This number allowed me to both explore how freelancers in their own contexts see autonomy and algorithmic control, and to make a more meaningful comparison between the two countries. The sample also represented different types of freelancers, including a few very successful ones, mid-level workers, and newcomers. The motivation behind this diversity was to show a real-world situation in which disparate people think in terms of autonomy and algorithmic control rather than showing just what the best workers are thinking.

3.3.1 Addressing Sampling Bias

There are several biases associated with recruiting workers through online freelancer communities that I tried to address. Freelancers using Facebook groups, Telegram channels, and LinkedIn groups may be more digitally comfortable, more experienced, or more successful than others on these platforms. The latter bias is particularly relevant to research on platform labour and warrants acknowledgement. In an attempt to recruit a diverse range of workers, I sought contacts with different levels of experience on the platform. For example, when reviewing posts, I noticed that some of the most engaged and active discussions online revolved around issues of low visibility, rejected proposals or trouble finding one's first client. I contacted these workers directly to ensure that the sample was not only drawn from workers who were succeeding on the platform. Snowball sampling also helps address homophily bias, in which participants simply introduce you to others like them. For example, if a highly rated worker referred me to other high-rated workers, they have been incentivised by the same systems, that is, have high levels of autonomy and share very similar experiences, understandings and perceptions of platform controls. When soliciting referrals, I therefore asked contacts for workers at different experience levels, including newer workers, mid-level workers, and those who had recently struggled with ratings or visibility issues.

3.3.2 Definition of Group

In this study, "workers in specific socio-economic contexts" refers to freelancers based in Ghana and South Africa, countries that provide different settings for interpreting and managing issues of autonomy, risk, and algorithmic control on platforms like Upwork. Ghana falls within the general West African tendency towards informal employment relations and weak worker protection, while South Africa, having comprehensive formal protection of workers, experiences high rates of structural unemployment. In this study, the definition of the group provides an anchor for sampling, namely, it was important not

merely to recruit current working users of Upwork but also to select people from distinct national labour systems that may produce such differentiated experiences.

3.4 Comparative Case Study

This study uses a comparative case study of freelancers in Ghana and South Africa on the online platform Upwork. This is a Ghana and South Africa freelancers case study report. Using a comparative case study methodology enables one to explore in detail how freelancers in different countries interpret autonomy and negotiate algorithmic control on Upwork. The objective is to show the imposition of platform architectures in the gig economy in very different labour market structures, national labour laws, and socio-economic contexts. Through a comparative approach, the study highlights how platform-based work manifests in various countries and how control is exercised in a global online workplace.

This paper investigates how freelancers in Ghana and South Africa navigate and interact with the digital rules enforced by algorithms on freelance platforms. The reason for the comparison is that labour market conditions, institutions, and social contexts in the two countries affect how workers respond to the enforcement of digital rules on the platform in different ways. Platform work is always interpreted in relation to prior employment experiences, employment relations, and labour market conditions. Therefore, it is essential to empirically examine how the latter influences workers' engagement with platforms and digital labour market rules. Freelancers who use online freelance platforms can engage in the online economy from any location they prefer, experiencing a new type of work environment that they do not physically control.

These institutional environments were consequently key to understanding why they are able to use or interpret the same platform rules differently. Since formal protections under labour law and an organised trade union movement are more deeply entrenched in South Africa than in Ghana, South African often interpreted platform rules against the backdrop of institutional alternatives, whereas Ghanaian freelancers viewed the identical platform as an economic necessity (ILO, 2021). Occupational category is also relevant to this analysis. The experiences of freelancers are not only affected by the national context in which they are situated but also by the kind of work that they undertake on the platform. Choice of occupational category will also be likely to influence the degree of flexibility and autonomy experienced by the freelancer on the platform, which will depend on the kind of employment contract the freelancer successfully negotiated with the client, and the extent to which the client's ability to negotiate a particular kind of work contract was

limited. Although the socioeconomic context helps explain differences in interpretations of labour institutions, it plays a much larger role in experiences on the platforms. Workers in highly specialised or in-demand fields may have more scope to negotiate how work is performed, while lower-entry or more competitive fields might face greater external pressures, such as ranking and client judgment. This means that experiences of platform control are likely to vary not only between Ghana and South Africa, but also across different forms of freelance work within each case, with **Figure 2** clearly shows data on online labour distribution and occupational differences between Ghana and South Africa.

Source: OLI 2020 | onlinelabourobservatory.org

Figure 2. Distribution of Online Labour by Occupation

Taken together, the comparative case study design makes it possible to examine how the same platform structures are filtered through different labour market and occupational contexts. This provides a stronger basis for understanding how freelancers interpret autonomy, respond to algorithmic control, and make sense of their working conditions on Upwork.

3.5 Data Analysis Method

All interviews were conducted in English and transcribed verbatim using Turboscribe. Then I used an iterative approach, reading the transcripts repeatedly to identify the codes. This research uses a reflexive thematic analysis approach (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This approach is relevant to our research question, as it addresses the processes of making meaning, how freelancers make sense of their experience of autonomy, and how they cope with the algorithmic control imposed on them by platforms. The analysis proceeded

through four interconnected stages. In the first stage, the transcripts were read and re-read to see how the freelancers described the working practices, rules, and decision-making on the platform. This involved calling attention to the different facets of these practices, such as their varying degrees of visibility, the advantages of their flexibility with clients, and the pressure of always being online.

The initial coding refers to the first codes that came up inductively; it means that they will not be developed a priori but rather from the data. As soon as I produced the preliminary array of codes, I started amalgamating to create a larger analytical picture. The codes “entry as necessity” and “connects as financial burden” were brought together under the entry conditions theme. Furthermore, the codes “JSS uncertainty” and “unpaid effort” were grouped under limited autonomy. I produced a clear map to show this transition from data to analysis; **Table 1** shows how the specific codes were organised into final research themes.

Table 1. Overview of Analytical Themes

Analytical Theme	Associated Initial Codes (Core focus)
1 Entry and the Conditions of Platform Work	Entry as necessity; occupational differences, search for global clients; high competition at entry; Connects as financial burden.
2 Freedom with Conditions: How Autonomy Works in Practice	Autonomy with limits; JSS uncertainty; staying visible through unpaid effort; algorithmic surveillance
3 Expanding Work, Staying Silent	Scope expansion, fear of bad reviews, keeping quiet to protect profile scores, and client-worker power imbalance.
4 Working from the Margins:	Location-based doubt; institutional absence or mismatch; community support; infrastructure challenges.

To enable the execution of critical and comparative analysis of the data generated from the two selected sites, the themes were explored more deeply for each country and then compared between sites in Ghana and South Africa, as provided under the study research questions and objectives. To check for sense and credibility, each theme was reviewed against the data. They were mentioned by at least two participants. I revised and clarified these categories to ensure that each theme reflected a distinct aspect of the autonomy-control relationship without overlap. The ultimate terms assigned to the themes were

chosen to be as close to the participants' accounts as was humanly possible while remaining clear and analytical. The themes generated in this stage were then used as a basis for comparative analysis as to how freelance workers in Ghana and South Africa navigate and interpret the Upwork platform.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The participants received an informed consent form before I began my data collection. The form contained information about the purpose of the research and how participants were required to participate. It also detailed the time participants would need to spend on the interviews and that they would remain anonymous. Participants were also given the option to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. I obtained verbal consent from participants at the beginning of each interview. Their real names were replaced with pseudonyms in the transcripts to ensure their anonymity, and identifiable information was removed from the sound files and transcripts. The audio files and transcripts were then saved to password-protected media and I also ensured that participants' involvement in the study would not harm their reputations.

3.7 Limitations of study

Given that the participants were 18 freelancers from Ghana and South Africa working on Upwork, the findings are not representative of all platform workers in Ghana and South Africa or across the African continent. Upwork is the largest and most well-known online global freelancing platform, but its rules, moderation practices, evaluation systems, and algorithms represent only one type of remote knowledge-work platform. These findings will be most relevant to other freelance workers on platforms where tasks are mediated through ratings, profiles, bidding, and reputation. Most of the participants for this study are based in Accra and Johannesburg, but there are many other towns and rural areas across Africa where platform work is taking place. Workers in these areas may have very different experiences of platform work, however, as access to stable internet, electricity, and professional networks can vary greatly. The study has limitations in that it relies on the interpretations of the freelance workers in the study as opposed to direct observation of the platform's algorithm or interviews with clients. While the study does not attempt to understand the platform's intentions, private feedback from clients, or the actual mechanics behind the Job Success Score, it does explore how freelance workers understand autonomy and control in their work, as appropriate for the research question. Further research could incorporate the perspectives of clients and workers in other African countries.

4. Results

This chapter presents the analytical findings on how freelancers in Ghana and South Africa interpreted and navigated their working lives on the Upwork platform. The chapter is organised comparatively, but not in a mechanical way. Each theme is first explored through an analysis of how the two country contexts were represented by the participants. In other words, each theme first shows how participants from Ghana and South Africa described the same issue in relation to platform work. Importantly, however, each theme is then explored in a more nuanced way to show that, although there are key differences between Ghana and South Africa in how platform work is represented by participants, a Ghana-versus-South-Africa analysis is more complex than that. Upwork's global architecture of work exposed workers in both countries to a similar set of pressures, including initial invisibility, anxiety around Job Success Scores, unpaid visibility work, the imbalance of power between workers and clients, and the fear of receiving negative reviews from clients. Yet these shared pressures were not experienced by workers in both countries in the same way. The particular ways in which platform control was interpreted and absorbed by workers were shaped by several factors, including their specific occupation, their degree of income dependency, their prior experiences of platform work, and the range of exit options available to them.

4.1 Entry and the Conditions of Platform Work

The first theme relates to what participants described in joining Upwork, the things that attracted them to joining and what they met with at the beginning. Not only did entry conditions differ between Ghana and South Africa, but different entry conditions also played out within each country, which shaped how participants later interpreted and navigated platform rules.

4.1.1 Why They Joined and What They Found

The majority of Ghanaian subjects positioned their decision to join Upwork in terms of need. Many participants characterized local jobs as unstable, poorly paid and/or difficult to access, while they described the platform as the most viable option available to them, rather than a freely chosen one. The virtual assistant Efua described her situation like this:

“The pay was not encouraging, so I had to look for other options. Upwork was like the best option I could get to try.” (Efua, Ghana, VA)

“...So when I joined Upwork, it was really because I wanted more consistency and more reach.” (Lebo, South Africa, Web designer)

It’s worth noting that while many Ghanaian participants framed Upwork in this way, as a backup option and not the preferred method, not all held this view. According to Sena, a UI/UX designer from Accra, the platform’s experience is more mixed. While there were certain months when Upwork had almost fully taken on his earnings, there were also months where he was earning next to nothing from Upwork and was relying on local work to make up for it. His account, therefore, sat closest to the supplementary pattern more characteristic of South African respondents, suggesting that the level of dependence on Upwork as a source of income varied by occupational type and career stage among the Ghanaian respondents.

In contrast, participants from South Africa tended to view Upwork as a means of supplementing their existing work, or accessing clients worldwide. Lebo has commented that he joined Upwork in search of “more consistency and more reach,” which indicates this orientation. In Ghana, participants often cited labour market necessity as the reason for entering the platform while in South Africa, participants largely professed the desire to expand their work or professional activity, or earn a better income, as the reason for entering the platform. However, it was not so absolute. Ronewa, a South African graphic designer, said that there were times when Upwork was her main source of income, especially between jobs. Her narrative challenges the straightforward Ghana/South Africa dichotomy, demonstrating how South African participants could equally experience dependency on the platform when the offline options were weakened. The intra group differences are important analytically as income dependency shaped how informants subsequently interpreted the algorithmic penalties and client demands, which was common across the four themes.

An initial point of interest in cross-national comparison is the opening question asked of all 18 participants in Ghana and South Africa: despite being visible on the platform, workers reported being invisible to clients. This was due to several factors, including the absence of reviews and of a work history on their profile. Godfrey, a Ghanaian web developer, captured this precisely: 'Nobody knows you, so you have no reviews, no history, and no one trusts you.' Ronewa described the same experience in Johannesburg: 'You create a profile, upload your portfolio, write proposals, and then nothing happens.' There is, however, an important similarity between the two cases. It appears that the conditions of entry on Upwork are mainly controlled by the platform itself, rather than by country. The key difference between the two cases therefore, lies

with the resources available to participants in order to complete the initial period of entry on the platform.

4.1.2 Occupational Position and Exposure to Platform Pressure

Occupational category shaped how participants experienced platform pressure in ways that cut across national lines. Workers in high-competition, lower-barrier categories described harsher entry conditions than those in more specialised fields. Tony, a content writer in Ghana, explained:

“In content writing, there is a lot of competition. Reviews and profile trust become even more important. If I were in a tighter niche, maybe I would have more room to push back.” (Tony, Ghana, content writer)

Naledi, a copywriter from South Africa also referred to the pressure in generic content writing but presented it as an oversaturated field where scores and reviews matter more than in specialised writing. Tony’s account of platform pressure as described in the generic freelance writing field can be seen to transcend country and to be attached to certain forms of occupational categories of work. On the other hand, accounts from two of the designers, Sena from Ghana and Nadi from South Africa, speak to a different sort of pressure that they experience as against Tony’s description of pressure as bargaining for lower pay with clients wanting to interfere in the design process and offer designers the option of designing in different ways and of the designers being pressed to complete design according to clients’ design decisions. These accounts do not necessarily point to a universal experience of platform pressure amongst the designers but suggest that how this pressure is experienced is in large part determined by the type of work that the freelancer does and the degree of competition involved in that type of work and the room that workers have to negotiate with clients. These accounts show that the kind of work freelancers do shapes the degree of competition they face and the room they have to negotiate with clients. In other words, occupational differences are not fully explained by country context, but they interact with it.

4.1.3 The Hidden Financial Cost of Getting Started

The Connects system, through which freelancers must spend in-platform currency to submit proposals, was identified as a structural entry cost that affected participants across both countries. Bismark, a Ghanaian ghostwriter, described this as the real stress of beginning on the platform:

“The real stress was also the Connects side, spending money on every proposal and then receiving nothing. I spent a significant amount on proposals for jobs that looked perfect for me, and sometimes the client never hired anyone.” (Bismark, Ghana, ghostwriter)

Participants from South Africa described connects as exerting financial and strategic pressure but framed the story somewhat differently. According to Lebo, he has gradually become aware of which postings are likely to generate responses and which are not, managing the cost of connects as a strategy. Economic position manifests itself in framing. For Ghanaians, lacking other income options, spending connects on failed proposals represented a material loss. For South African respondents with additional income sources, the same expenditure was more of an optimization problem. Although the mechanism was universal, the stakes to which it attached differed by economic position (Newlands, 2021). This is shown directly in **Figure 3**.

Data Analysis Support for Entrepreneurship Research

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Summary
 I am an entrepreneurship professor seeking a skilled data analyst to assist in analyzing data collected from various classes. The ideal candidate will help interpret findings, generate insights, and present the results in a clear and concise manner. Familiarity with educational data analysis and statistical software is preferred. If you have a strong background in data analysis and a passion for education, I would love to hear from you!

I use the theory of planned behavior and collect pre/post data to measure the impact of education on entrepreneurial intention.

I am looking for someone that is interested in working with me on a number of projects. I have collected data from various schools around the world.

I look forward to hearing from you

Cheers,

You'll need Connects to bid.
 They're like credits that show clients you're serious.
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Buy Connects to apply

Save job

Flag as inappropriate

Send a proposal for: 16 Connects
 Available Connects: 0

About the client

- Payment method verified
- Phone number verified

United States
 Pittsburgh 10:16 PM

Figure 3. Upwork job posting requiring Connects to apply.

Overall, the findings in this theme show that entry into Upwork was conditioned by national context, occupational category, dependency on income, and the cost structures of the platform, and that these conditions were not uniform in either country. There were similarities across the countries as well as differences, particularly around not being visible at first and the pressure from Connects. The succeeding themes are interconnected with both patterns.

4.2 Freedom with Conditions: How Autonomy Works in Practice

The second theme addresses the central tension in the research question: how do freelancers interpret and experience the autonomy that platform work promises? Across all eighteen participants, a real form of freedom was acknowledged. But that freedom was consistently narrated as bounded, conditional and often significantly narrower than expected. Three dimensions

of this conditionality recurred across both countries: the relational nature of autonomy under income dependency, the opacity of the Job Success Score and its behavioural effects and the unpaid work of staying visible.

4.2.1 Autonomy as Conditional and Relational

There were several points of agreement among participants from both Ghana and South Africa regarding freedom. First, the platform enabled participants to work as and when they pleased; there was no need for a physical office, and working hours were flexible. However, when it came to how participants actually experienced this freedom, there was less agreement. Most participants went on to describe how, despite initial freedom, it was curtailed in many ways. In many instances, participants held two contradictory positions within a single interview, describing the freedom that existed for them as participants and how this ‘freedom’ was restricted. An example was Godfrey, a Ghanaian web developer. When asked whether freelancing meant being his own boss, he replied: 'I might say yes. Then in some cases I say no.' He explained that he could choose which jobs to apply for and was not physically supervised, but added, 'There is still very much pressure. It is just quieter.' This self-contradiction within a single participant's account is worth dwelling on. It shows that the autonomy-control tension is not resolved in favour of one side but held in genuinely ambivalent terms in everyday platform work. South African participants described the same coexistence using a different language. Lebo offered a precise account:

“There is some form of freedom, yes. But at the same time there is another type of control. It is not direct like a manager standing over you, but it is there.” (Lebo, South Africa, web developer)

“To be honest, I tried to manage it very quietly, because I did not want any problems. You see, you get a client, you want the person to be a repeat customer. So I kept adjusting myself.” (Francesca, Ghana, Virtual assistant)

This formulation, regardless of country, the experience of freedom and of invisible control was framed in the same way by participants: freedom alongside constraint. What varied was the language used to describe the constraint. While in Ghana, participants framed constraints more as how things worked or as a condition of participation, in South Africa, participants more frequently named the constraint and framed it as a structural feature that they were managing to negotiate on the platform. The experience of participants was thus similar, but framed in very different ways by the two groups of participants, depending on the institutionalised framework through which they made sense of their experience on the platform (Jarrahi et al., 2020).

4.2.2 The Job Success Score: Important but Not Transparent

Participants across both countries identified the Job Success Score as one of the most consequential and anxiety-producing features of platform work, and the opacity of its calculation sharpened the anxiety. Mike, a Ghanaian logo designer, described a score drop after a contract he believed had gone well:

“...everything was looking okay, they left five stars, no drama in messages. Later I saw that my Job Success Score was dropping. Then I wondered how.” (Mike, Ghana, designer)

Similarity in the account of Lebo in South Africa of a public contract that looked successful and then score dropped is described in the following words: “they gave me five stars, so I thought everything was good. But then after that my score dropped. So obviously there must have been some private feedback that I did not see.” Similarity in the structure of accounts in two countries where JSS opacity is present across countries and therefore likely to be a platform-driven mechanism as opposed to country-specific. The level of anxiety that this experience causes varies though and is more intense with participants who have greater income dependency on the platform. For participants who rely heavily on Upwork for their income, the JSS is not just a number on their profile page. It is connected to their future work on the platform and to their ability to earn a steady income. Even a small drop in score is perceived to be serious by participants who rely heavily on the platform for their income. Participants who have other sources of income are concerned with their JSS but the level of fear that they express regarding its impact is less than that of participants who are more dependent on the platform. Nadi a 98% JSS UI/UX designer from South Africa provided the most analytically precise account of her long-term account on the platform.

“You get used to living inside patterns you do not fully understand. That is part of the problem.” (Nadi, South Africa, UI/UX designer)

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4.2.3 The Unpaid Work of Staying Visible

In both locations, the unpaid work of remaining visible appeared, though not experienced in exactly the same way. Participants from Ghana on average offered a description of this in terms of searching costs born of limited income alternatives. For them, reading job posts, writing proposals, improving profiles, and spending Connects were not ordinary things of freelancing. They were indeed a direct risk because they could burn up little money and still produce no contract. Ghanaian virtual assistant Efua epitomized the fact clearly:

"A lot of time goes into this... you spend time reading the job, you spend time writing proposals... but there is no guarantee." (Efua, Ghana, virtual assistant)

South African participants described the same type of unpaid labour but more often stressed the timing and strategy of staying visible during quiet periods. They adjusted timing for proposals, refreshed their portfolios, responded quickly, and tried to stay active on their profiles. Ronewa, a South African graphic designer, explained the frustration in simple terms:

"You can work all day and still feel like you did not really earn anything." (Ronewa, South Africa, graphic designer)

The difference was not that one group performed unpaid visibility labour and the other did not; both groups did. A disparity in the value placed on this labour by participants from each country is made clear by this comparison. In Ghana, labour is mostly framed as financially burdensome and in the absence of alternatives to pay Connects, whereas in South Africa, it is framed strategically and as temporally burdensome in terms of timing, of how to be responsive, and of profile management. There was no absolute distinction. Sena, a UI/UX designer from Ghana, also spoke of changing his working hours to those of his clients closer to the times of South African accounts. The experience was also influenced by the occupational category and client base. All in all, unpaid visibility work was a common feature of Upwork, but the meaning of that

unpaid work varied by income dependency, occupation, and country context (Newlands, 2021).

Figure 4. Proposal status Upwork. Source: (Mike, Ghana)

4.3 Expanding Work, Staying Silent: Client Control and the Fear of Bad Reviews

The third theme was a form of control, not of the platform but rather in the relationship between freelancers and clients. Participants from both countries frequently described scope creep, or work done beyond contract terms, and the silencing effect of the review system in ways that were often strikingly similar. However, the degree and character of constraint varied by occupational position, income dependency and platform vulnerability.

4.3.1 How Clients Directed the Work

Client control was established in both countries, but participants did not always use the same words. Ghanaian participants frequently depicted client direction as something to tactically manage in order to maintain work, protect reviews, and manage their relationship with the client. Francesca, a virtual assistant from Ghana, recalls how she reacted after a client kept adding more tasks to the deal:

"I kept adjusting myself. I did not want to lose the client either."
(Francesca, Ghana, virtual assistant)

This account demonstrates that client control was not perceived solely as direct instruction. Dependence on repeat work and fear of being seen as difficult also connected with this. The worker appreciated that the work was expanding but practically responded by remaining quiet and adaptable, given there would be future ratings and incomes. Participants in South Africa also reported strong client direction, but they more frequently labelled it a work organization and

fairness problem. Bongani, a sales support worker from South Africa, recorded this directly:

"Clients have a lot of control over my work... they can shape the scripts, the time, the tools you use...the client is really the one in charge in everything." (Bongani, South Africa, sales support)

This country comparison is therefore particularly clear. While several Ghanaian freelancers viewed client control over when they could work and what rate of pay they could receive as part of the normal price of keeping their Upwork income coming, South African participants framed this pressure differently: as an imbalance in the work process which they could identify even as they went along with it. Again, this does not mean to say that the Ghanaian participants included here had seen no difficulties with client control, nor that the South African participants here were able to resist client control easily. But what their comments do reveal is to highlight that the same client power is read through the different practical and institutional expectations that are current in the two countries. The review system on platform work, for example, makes client power stronger, because a freelancer's disagreement with a client could have repercussions in future contracts: through the ratings, reviews and profile visibility that reflect that freelancer's past disputes with clients.

4.3.2 Scope Creep and the Incremental Expansion of Contracts

The most mentioned type of client-driven control in the dataset is scope creep. Relatedly, this client-driven control was reported in relation to every occupational category and both countries. It is the mechanism of the system that makes it analytically interesting: each addition is reasonable in its own right, and it is only when they accumulate that the transformation of the original contract becomes visible. At that stage, the freelancer generally has enough vested in the relationship to perceive contestation as more pricey than continued compliance (Huang et al., 2024). Efua's account of a VA contract that started with inbox management put the accumulation nicely:

"The work started expanding... and then document formatting, even some social media posting. It just kept on growing like that." (Efua, Ghana, virtual assistant)

Thandi, a South African virtual assistant, described a trajectory almost identical to Efua's: inbox support became customer follow-up, travel booking, lead tracking, and last-minute weekend reminders. The two cases of virtual assistance listed above demonstrated situations where 'scope creep' is most prone to occur; in scenarios where tasks lend themselves to be difficult at first and then subsequently adaptable. Virtual assistance work already has many

flexible elements in terms of timing, and the virtual environment creates the illusion of near instant responses and can prompt a considerable amount of informal communication that is granted automatically through trust of the client. Work such as the UI/UX design discussed by Sena is very different. Specialised work does not normally enable the same amount of scope creep by clients as less specialised tasks that can simply be ‘taken on’. Although the client has considerable influence over the design, the particular combination of highly technical as well as creative elements means that, although informal requests for changes can be gradually ‘tuned in to’ by the designer, in reality, most client influence is for frequent updates, alternative suggestions, further iterations of the current design, and so on. Such influence manifests itself differently than in work with less specialised skills, that is, as a desire to intervene in processes rather than to have extra tasks that are not covered in the original agreement.

4.3.3 The Rating System as a Silencing Mechanism

The most telling dimension of client control was how the anticipated review shaped behaviour during the contract itself, before any review was given. Tony, a Ghanaian content writer, captured this precisely:

“A review is not just something that comes at the end. It sits in the room with you while you are working. It affects how patient you are, how much you explain, and how careful you become.” (Tony, Ghana, content writer)

Ghanaian participant Francesca decoded what the rating system was actually measuring: “The client has to score you, in a sense, based on the job you did for them, how compliant you were, and all that.” The phrase “how compliant you were” is analytically precise. This indicates that the rating system assesses both relational acquiescence and technical quality, and that this understanding has informed professional behavior accordingly.

South African participants described the same silencing dynamic, though not always with the same intensity. Ronewa, a graphic designer, offered an account that explicitly named the trade-off being made:

“I knew it was beyond the original agreement..., but because I was still trying to protect my score, I was thinking more about the review than about the fairness of the situation.” (Ronewa, South Africa, graphic designer)

Ronewa's account differs from Francesca's in one analytically important respect: she names fairness as a category that the review calculation overrides. She has a normative framework for identifying unfairness but calculates that the cost of contestation is too high. For Francesca, the workings of the platform were not framed in terms of fairness. She interpreted the platform's workings in terms of the divergent institutional reference points between South Africa and Ghana, where the research took place. South African participants were aware

of labour rights and dispute-resolution processes, even if these did not extend to platform work. In contrast, for Ghanaian participants, the platform's rules were simply the rules governing access to it. Within the South African group of participants, there was variation on this theme. Nadi described her management of a scope expansion during her quiet period on the platform. She had handled it 'carefully' to avoid making the quiet period worse. Nadi had the normative framework for her quiet period but used it in ways I had not anticipated. Even a well-positioned South African worker with a JSS at 98% is forced at some point by platform and client ratings together. Silence around the rules of access to work on platforms is therefore maintained to varying degrees by workers in different circumstances, and they use different frameworks to make sense of the silence.

4.4 Working from the Margins: Location, Lack of Protection, and How Freelancers Cope

The fourth theme discusses the wider structural conditions that shaped freelancers' experiences in both countries. The location of origin produced forms of pre-professional scrutiny. Both countries had national labour institutions, but they were unable to reach platform workers. Freelancers in both contexts created informal community networks that provided platform literacy and emotional solidarity, although not formal recourse.

4.4.1 Location as a Structural Disadvantage

Participants in both countries described experiences of geographic scrutiny that preceded any professional interaction. In Ghana, this took the form of authenticity doubt. Bismark, a ghostwriter in Accra, described clients questioning language authenticity and professional reliability before seeing a single work sample:

“Some clients question your reliability, your internet stability, or the authenticity of your English before they even get a chance to read a single sample. Before you even begin, you are already proving something.” (Bismark, Ghana, ghostwriter)

This contrasts with other locations, where location-based scrutiny is less closely tied to everyday problems in South Africa. Zibo, a data analyst, said that his clients are already asking questions about load-shedding and internet connections at the very start of the consultation. “Those questions may sound practical, but they also remind you of where you come from.” There is a platform-wide structural similarity in which questions about location and credibility are addressed before competence can be considered, that is, before one can assess the value of the work a person can do. Such a structural similarity

is well studied and can be distinguished from the content of prejudice that is location-specific (Van Slageren et al., 2022). Within the South African group, Nadi described location bias as present but not dramatic every time, while for Ronewa it was a very consistent way in which he realised first impressions of himself as a worker. Platform-wide reputation and workers' profile history will always partially compensate for location-based credibility losses, yet such losses are by no means completely erased.

4.4.2 Institutional Gaps: Labour Law and Platform Governance

Across both countries, the study found that there was no formal institutional framework that offered platform workers any meaningful protection. Ghanaian participants called this structural absence. Bismark made a candid remark in which he stated: 'There might be labour laws on paper, but for someone working with overseas clients via a US-based platform, those laws do not feel close. You are essentially on your own.' A South African participant noted regulatory mismatch, not absence. All South African participants were aware by name of the Commission for Conciliation, Mediation and Arbitration, but all concluded it was irrelevant to their situation. Lebo clearly drew this:

"I know the CCMA, yes... As a freelancer on an international platform, I don't really feel those formal structures are made for situations like mine." (Lebo, South Africa, web developer)

The comparison reveals that, although neither country had meaningful institutional protection, the nature of that lack differed between the two. Ghanaian participants were in a condition of Structural Absence, whereas South African participants experienced a regulatory mismatch. The bottom line: in both cases, the outcome was very similar; the freelancer had no institutional means to seek a remedy if he or she was rated unfairly, experienced scope creep, or was not paid. South Africa has a stronger tradition of trade unionism than Ghana, and there have been some attempts to organise platform workers in location-based sectors (Webster & Masikane, 2023). However, in neither setting was formal collective action found among the online knowledge workers: first, they were likely classified as contractors, thereby excluded from collective bargaining rights; second, they are geographically dispersed and, therefore, less likely to be able to form solidarity than a co-located workforce.

4.4.3 Informal Networks and How Freelancers Cope

In the absence of formal institutional protection, freelancers in both countries had built WhatsApp groups and Telegram channels that functioned as the primary practical infrastructure of their platform working lives. Kojo, a

Ghanaian digital marketer, described the epistemological function of these communities alongside the practical:

“Even hearing that other people are also trying to understand the same unclear system helps. It does not remove the uncertainty, but it makes it easier to carry because you realise it is not only happening to you.” (Kojo, Ghana, digital marketer)

This account particularly highlights the reframing function of community networks, in which individual difficulty becomes a shared structure of difficulty, making it possible to go on. One could describe the same function with varying emphasis for South African people. Communities were her most valuable asset, the one she was most comfortable with and where she had found more stability. Nadi was most concerned with controlling her emotions and not panicking during periods of quiet. Thandi, a South African virtual assistant, represented the affective dimension with: 'Otherwise, the work will feel very lonely. When there are other people that you can console and confide in, it helps you shape your career better.' Ronewa, whose income had varied more over time, valued most the insight the networks delivered: client warnings, insights into proposal timing and scoring observations. The within-South Africa variation revealed that freelancers' most desired contribution from the communities varied with their platform circumstances.

The limits of these networks were identified consistently across both countries. Efua offered the clearest formulation:

“They help. They just help. They do not remove the pressure completely. They just help you notice the problem earlier.” (Efua, Ghana, virtual assistant)

Noticing the problem earlier is not institutional protection. A freelancer with an unfair review cannot resolve that through a WhatsApp group or Telegram group. The informal infrastructure fills the void left by formal institutions without substituting for what they would provide (Anwar & Graham, 2021). Taken together, the findings in this theme show that formal institutions in neither country provided meaningful protection for platform workers, while informal community networks offered solidarity and practical knowledge without being able to substitute for institutional recourse.

4.5 Summary

The findings across the four themes show that the Ghana-South Africa comparison remains meaningful, but only when it is held together with similarities produced by the platform itself. In comparison, Upwork is viewed in significantly different ways by Ghanaian workers and South African freelancers. Ghanaian workers view the platform as a necessary response to the lack of opportunities available and the institutional absence that characterises

their country. South African workers, on the other hand, view Upwork as supplementary to their current income. However, they view it as fair and are upset about it in terms of the way in which the platform exerts pressure on the workers and a regulatory mismatch. However, despite these differences, there are also some similarities work, the Connects costs, uncertainty about how the JSS was implemented, the amount power of the client rating, and the weak formal redress mechanisms that exist on the platform all have of unpaid work or visibility labour that is involved, the amount of scope creep that there is, the an impact on the lives of workers in Ghana and South Africa. The differences in how these issues are occupational and platform-specific factors. This balance is interpreted in the Discussion chapter in the context of the labour control system and the literature on platform work in the Global South.

5. Discussion

This study explored the experiences of freelancers in Ghana and South Africa as they navigate the tension between the autonomy they yearn for and the control they face on the global platform Upwork. Using qualitative comparative study, this study revealed both differences and similarities in how freelancers from Ghana and South Africa make sense of their work on the Upwork platform. Importantly, the study reveals that while freelancers from Ghana and South Africa drew upon different interpretive resources in making sense of their work on Upwork, these differences were, in turn, masked by a similar set of platform mechanisms that governed their work. Importantly, while all freelancers on the platform were subjected to the same set of mechanisms, including the opacity of the JSS, the high costs of Connects, the increasing scope of work that clients wanted freelancers to do, the work of visibility that freelancers were required to undertake in order to get work on the platform, and the fear of negative reviews from clients, these mechanisms had different effects on freelancers in Ghana and South Africa. Overall, this study shows that global platform control is interpreted through freelancers' countries and occupational positions. Consistent with studies on algorithmic management on digital platforms, controls work through design systems that frame and regulate the work process independently of direct supervision (Rahman, 2021; Rosenblat & Stark, 2016).

These design systems, therefore, function as technical control systems that reflect Edwards' (1979) idea of technical control. The JSS system, private feedback, and, in particular, connects scores on Upwork operate similarly for freelancers in Ghana and South Africa when workers adapt to platform rules to remain visible. However, the same architecture of technical control systems on Upwork can carry very different meanings for workers, depending on the national context in which the platform is used. In the case of the JSS, for example, the opaque scoring system and the high costs of submitting proposals through the JSS threaten Ghanaian participants' livelihoods on the platform. For South African participants on the platform, the same mechanisms posed strategic problems that had to be managed. The architecture of Upwork, therefore, enables similar constraints on freelancers around the world to be experienced by workers in different ways and with different stakes.

The results also show that this self-regulation took a form close to Barker's (1993) concept of concertive control, in which workers' self-regulation is internalised and continuously monitored by them. Similar to Blyth et al. (2022) on Upwork self-branding, where workers manage their online profiles, communicate with clients and manage their online reputation anticipating

evaluation by the latter, the workers in this study anticipated and prepared for sanctions that might be put in place by the platform in order to avoid bad reviews or a drop in JSS that could negatively affect their earnings in the future. Thus, there is a similarity in the self-regulation by the workers studied, which is also shared but differentiated. The two groups of workers used different vocabularies of interpretation to explain their behaviour of anticipating the platform's sanctions before they occur. The Ghanaian workers explained their actions on the platform in terms of how they could survive on it. On the other hand, the South African workers explained their actions on the platform in terms of the platform's indirect control over them or its unfairness.

Building on this research into precarious work, and how control is perceived by those in precarious work, we have found that certain aspects of the experience of control are determined by the position of the individual within the wider labour market, and that where few alternatives to platform work exist, workers feel a very strong sense of monitoring and of dependency, which can be particularly difficult for individuals to resist (Kalleberg & Vallas, 2018; Standing, 2010). However, the study has examined how the experience of control is shaped by the national context in which platform work occurs. Specifically, in countries with a long-standing formal labour-rights-based institution, but where high levels of unemployment and a large number of working-age people are excluded from these protections in practice, the reality for workers is very different from that often described in academic literature. The research described here confirms that, in terms of labour market and platform monitoring, certain aspects of workers' experience of control in earning income on Upwork are particularly resistant to change. But it also revealed that income dependency on the platform is not perceived identically in Ghana and South Africa, with while Upwork appears to be economically necessary for many in Ghana, in South Africa, the platform is viewed in a number of ways, with the most common being as supplementary income, or as a way to earn internationally. There are, however, a number of exceptions to this general trend, which are examined in more detail in the body of the report through the lens of the individual's specific occupation and their individualised history of earnings on the platform.

The findings from the Upwork study, particularly regarding scope creep, resonate with Braverman (1974) in his seminal work on work design and execution. The scope of work agreed for a particular task can very quickly be 'reworked' to incorporate further work within the remit of the initial task or even changes to the terms of reference for the work. In both countries, there is recognition of the extra work workers are asked to do, but workers' perceptions

of it differ considerably. In Ghana, the majority of workers recognised that to gain repeat business from clients, they must be able to accommodate extra work within the terms of the contract for the initial task. In South Africa, there was recognition of the extra work workers were asked to complete, but it was frequently deemed unfair. And while there were instances in which workers described being ‘used’ even when they recognised that the extra work was unfair, this was not the most common finding.

The formal recognition of workers’ rights does not always turn into reality for platform workers, whose rights are not formally recognised. However, as platform work is taking place in countries with a stronger labour rights tradition (South Africa) than Ghana, this translates into platformized ways of working in which workers always interpret their work in terms of resistance, given that on Upwork, their future earnings are tied to their rating. In this sense, the client functioned as a mechanism of labour control, as Korczynski (2001) argues in the context of service work, where client expectations can become part of labour control. Upwork intensified this dynamic by linking client evaluations to public reputation and algorithmic visibility. These results indicate two forms of weak protection for online platform workers, extending current research on platform work in the Global South (Anwar & Graham, 2021; Heeks et al., 2021). Also, there was a structural absence of institutions and support mechanisms in Ghana for online workers who deal with foreign clients and platform clients in the Global North. In South Africa, weak protection was attributed to a regulatory mismatch. While South African online freelancers were aware of institutions and of their right to fair treatment, they found that this did not translate to any form of protection while working online. This left them with no formal recourse to address issues of unfair online reviews, an increased or uncontrolled scope of work, and non-payment. There were, however, two key differences between the two groups of participants. Ghanaian participants described being on their own, while South African participants described being outside institutions that they nevertheless recognised. These two findings are among the clearest from our comparison between Ghana and South Africa.

The occupational category further complicates the country comparison. The findings imply that skill specialization affected the nature of client control. In both nations, virtual assistants have described expandable tasks, which makes them particularly prone to scope creep. Content writers in both countries referred to intense competition. Scores and reviews have become central because the category is crowded, so clients can easily compare many workers. UI/UX designers described a different kind of control where clients intervened

in the processes and decisions and asked for revisions rather than just adding other tasks. Skills matter because specialized work allows freelancers more space to define boundaries, whereas lower-barrier, less well-defined work makes it tougher to defend boundaries. Yet, skill did not remove control; it changed whether control appeared as task expansion, price competition, or process intervention.

This occupational variation does not replace country context; it interacts with it. A specialised worker with several income sources could treat client pressure as negotiable, while a worker with the same skill but deeper income dependency could still comply to avoid a negative review. This is why the findings should be read through three connected layers: platform architecture created common control mechanisms; national context shaped workers' expectations, vocabulary, and exit options; and occupational category shaped the concrete form that control took in everyday work. This layered interpretation preserves the comparative logic of the thesis while avoiding the over-simple claim that all Ghanaian workers or all South African workers experienced Upwork in the same way.

6. Conclusion

This study explored how Ghanaian and South African freelancers interpreted and navigated the tension between autonomy and control on the Upwork platform. A reflexive thematic analysis of 18 semi-structured interviews with knowledge workers yielded four main themes: 'entering platform work'; 'conditional autonomy, client control, and silence'; and 'working from the margins'. In conclusion, the Ghana-South Africa comparison is important, yet should be understood against the backdrop of the identical problems connected with Upwork's platform architecture. This finding aligns with broader findings in platform labour studies that platforms organise labour through mechanisms of rating, ranking, client feedback, and governance rather than managerial control (Gorwa, 2019; Rosenblat & Stark, 2016). Ghanaian participants more often attributed their entry into the platform to economic hardship, the absence of institutional protection, and 'coping alone'. South African participants more often defined the platform as a source of 'side-income', an opportunity for the international job market, and 'mismatch of fairness and legislation', referring to the platform's challenges. These differences indicate that individual understandings of the platform were shaped by labour market conditions and institutional frameworks in the countries, even though the platform remained formally identical. This result is consistent with arguments indicating that global platform labour should be understood not only through the lens of technology but also through the lens of the availability of labour alternatives and labour market conditions (Anwar & Graham, 2021; Graham et al., 2017).

However, the analysis of the findings indicates that the same mechanism of control was generated globally in both settings. Freelancers based in Ghana and South Africa detailed problems related to initial invisibility, costs of Connects, unclear JSS, unpaid visibility labour, scope creep caused by clients, and fear of negative reviews. According to Edwards (1979), technical control refers to the exertion of control over workers through the logic of work processes themselves, rather than through direct personal management. Having similar experiences does not mean that the experiences of workers in Ghana or South Africa are the same or those of the global North. Rather, African freelancers in the global south engage with global platforms from positions of little formal protection, limited recourse to redress, asymmetric bargaining power with international clients, and reliance on personal relations. The study's findings are in line with studies on online labour platforms. As per these studies, such platforms lead workers from the Global South to be fed into competitive markets and end up losing out on bargaining power, pay and visibility (Graham

et al., 2017; Howson et al., 2022). In many Global North countries, platform work exists alongside strong labour institutions and other sources of income. In our African cases, the degree to which platform workers are subjected to platform control is aggravated by their lack of exit options and formal redress (Anwar & Graham, 2021; Heeks et al., 2021).

makes three contributions to the literature on platform work. Firstly, it proves the importance of platform architecture: JSS, private feedback, connects, and review mechanisms put a similar form of pressure on behaviour in both countries. Such evidence backs up research into algorithmic management, which shows how platforms deploy opaque systems to shape worker behaviour while presenting these workers as formally independent contractors (Rosenblat & Stark, 2016; Rahman, 2021). Furthermore, this indicates that institutions are important even if they do not directly regulate platform workers. In South Africa, on-platform stronger labour rights did not help freelancers get protection; some were able to spot unfairness and mismatches when they saw them. In Ghana, where the sense of institutional absence was more severe, the terms and conditions of the platform became the rule that freelancers had to agree to in order to be allowed to continue on the platform. Lastly, the research underscores the importance of occupational categories in light of the nature of client control as determined through skill level-task boundary combinations. VAs faced task inflation, while content writers were more affected by competition and the need to meet review requirements. UI/UX designers faced process intervention. According to the literature on knowledge work, professional workers may enjoy a certain degree of occupational autonomy, yet they also confront less visible forms of control, including client control, performance expectations, and reputation mechanisms (Gandini, 2016; Sewell, 2005). The works imply a three-tiered structure of platform control. At the top level, global platform rules apply a set of standard pressures across countries. At the second level, country context determines how these pressures are interpreted and what kind of dependency on the platform results from this interpretation. At the last conceptual level, the nature of the occupation itself further determines the manifestation of this control on a day-to-day basis.

The paper also has real-world applications. If the JSS system were more transparent, and the private feedback provided, cost of proposals visible, and the visibility algorithms made more visible, workers would have clearer grounds for understanding and contesting their platform standing. But transparency of the platform alone is not enough. The findings suggest that platform control severity depends, in part, on what workers can access outside the platform. When formal labour markets offer reliable options and relevant

protections, platform regulations become more malleable. It becomes harder to challenge the same platform mechanisms when alternatives are weak, informal, or inaccessible. Due to this, platform regulation should be linked to labour-market policy more broadly, including protection for freelancers, clearer dispute channels for cross-border online work, and support for collective forms of representation for remote knowledge workers.

Implications for Future Research

The results are dependent on a number of limitations, which also indicate future research. The 18-member research participant sample is drawn mainly from Accra and Johannesburg and is not representative of all platform workers of Ghana and South Africa. People in smaller cities and rural areas may have different constraints, particularly on internet access, electricity, and professional networks. The emphasis on Upwork means that the results may not be relevant to platforms with different governance arrangements. The study finally explored how freelancers interpret platform work because it does not include clients and platform representatives or access to Upwork's internal scoring system. Consequently, future research might compare other countries in Africa, such as Nigeria, Kenya, or Egypt; examine other platforms and types of platform labour; adopt longitudinal designs to follow workers as their profiles change; and include the perspective of clients to see how rating practices, scope expansion, and expectations are justified from the other side of the platform relationship.

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Appendix A

Table 2. Participant Overview

Participants	Pseudonym	Country	City	Occupation	JSS (%)
1	Godfrey	Ghana	Kumasi	Web developer	89
2	Efua	Ghana	Accra	Virtual assistant	95
3	Samuel	Ghana	Accra	Data analyst	88
4	Francesca	Ghana	Accra	VA / Sales admin	91
5	Mike	Ghana	Accra	Logo designer	86
6	Bismark	Ghana	Accra	Ghostwriter	90
7	Tony	Ghana	Accra	Content writer	87
8	Kojo	Ghana	Accra	Digital marketer	81
9	Sena	Ghana	Accra	UI/UX designer	83
10	Lebo	South Africa	Johannesburg	Web developer	92
11	Ronewa	South Africa	Johannesburg	Graphic designer	93
12	Zibo	South Africa	Johannesburg	Data analyst	95
13	Thandi	South Africa	Johannesburg	Virtual assistant	89
14	Bongani	South Africa	Johannesburg	Sales support	88
15	Naledi	South Africa	Johannesburg	Copywriter	85
16	Nadi	South Africa	Johannesburg	UI/UX designer	98
17	Sipho	South Africa	Johannesburg	Digital marketer	84
18	Lungelo	South Africa	Johannesburg	Ghostwriter	87